

CHIKALATA CHA UTHENGA KWA MWINI WAKE NYUMBA

MUTU WA KAFUKUFUKU:

1i. The epidemiology of *E. coli* and non-typhoidal *Salmonella* at a household level in Malawi

CHIYAMBI

Ntchitoyi ikafufuza njira zimene tizirombo ta **bacteria** tozungulira nyumba timafalira, ndicholinga cha nthawi yaitali pofuna kuchepetsa kufala kwa matenda m' Malawi. Kuti tipange zimenezi tikupempha chilorezo chanu kuti titenge zoyesa za chimbudzi kuchokera kwa anthu okhala m'nyumba mwanu (ana anu onse komanso anhtu aakulu), nyama zimene zilipo komanso zimayang'aniridwa ndi mamembala a nyumbayi, nyama za kutchire komanso mbalame ndi zoyesa kuchokera mu za chilengedwe zozungulira nyumba. Tikukonzanso kuti tifufuze kupezeka kwa tizirombo toyambitsa matenda kuchokera ku nyama ku Chikwawa komanso Blantyre pogwiritsa ntchito zoyesa kuchokera ku nyama, komanso kupezeka kwa nyama, maka-maka mu ziweto (ngo'mbe, nkhusa ndi mbuzi) kunyama zimene zingathe kukhudza anthu komanso nyama, pounika zoyesa zochepa za magazi kuchokera ku nyama.

Dr Catherine Wilson, amene akugwira ntchitoyi, ndi dotolo wa nyama (veterinary surgeon) amene akukhala ku **University of Liverpool**, ndipo ntchitoyi ikupanga maphunziro ake a PhD. Iyeyu akugwira ntchito mogwirizana ndi malo oyezerako zinthu a **Liverpool-Malawi Wellcome Trust**, Blantyre, komanso International Livestock Research Institute, Kenya.

Zoyesa za chimbudzi zimene zatengedwa zidzatumizidwa ku malo oyezerako zinthu a **Liverpool-Malawi Wellcome Trust Laboratories**, Queen Elizabeth Hospital, Blantyre kumene ntchito yoyeza zinthu itadzachitikire. Bacteria amene amakuzidwa pa zoyesa, kapena DNA kuchokera ku ma bacteriawo, zidzatumizidwa ku UK kuti ntchito ya **whole genome sequencing** ikachitike. Zoyesa za magazi za nyama zikhoza kutumizidwa ku UK kuti zikagwiridwe ntchito, ngati pangapezeke kuti palibe Zoyeza zoyenelera ku Malawi. Palibe zoyesa za anthu zitadzatuluke m' Malawi.

KODI KAFUKUFUKUYU NDI WACHANI?

TENTACLE

Participant Information Sheet, English v2 29th January 2019

Zoyesa za chimbudzi zikutengedwa pofuna kuona ngati muli kachiroombo ka *E. coli* komanso **non-typhoidal Salmonella**. Ntchitoyi idzaphunzira za ubale umene ulipo pakati pa kachiroombo ka *E. coli* kopezeka mwa anthu komanso nyama. Kachiroombo ka Non-typhoidal *Salmonella* kamadzetsa imfa zokwera komanso matenda oopsya pakati pa anthu, maka-maka pakati pa ana komanso anthu achikulire. Kuonongeka kwa chilengedwe kudzera mu zoipa za chimbudz cha anthu kapena nyama zimene zimanyamula kachiroombo ka **bacteria**, ikhozanso kukhala imodzi mwa njira zimene matenda amafalikira m'nyumba. Pakali pano njira yeni-yeni imene kachiroombo ka bacteria kamafalira siikudziwika bwino.

Zoyesa kuchokera kwa anthu komanso nyama zam'nyumba, komanso chilengedwe zidzagwiritsidwa ntchito pofuna kuyesetsa kupeza m'mene kachiroombo ka *E. coli* komanso **non-typhoidal Salmonella** zimafalira m'nyumba.

Vuto la kusintha kwa kagwiridwe ntchito ka mankhwala amene amachiza matenda obwera chifukwa cha tizirombo ta bacteria (antimicrobial resistance) ndi vuto lalikulu dziko lonse lapansi. Zodandaulitsa ndizakuti, vutoli likuchepetsa chisankho pa thandizo loyenelera la mankhwala kwa anthu.

Tikapeza kuti nyama zikusonyeza kuti zili ndikuthekera koika anthu pa chiopyezo chotengera kachiroombo *E. coli*, non-typhoidal *Salmonella* komanso vuto la kusintha kwa kagwiridwe ntchito ka mankhwala amene amachiza matenda obwera chifukwa cha tizirombo ta bacteria (antimicrobial resistance determinants), tikapereka uphungu komanso thandizo kwa gulu la anthu m'dela pofuna kuchepetsa chiwerengero cha anthu amene angatengere matendawa, maka-maka ndi zimene zimabweretsa vuto la kusintha kwa kagwiridwe ntchito ka mankhwala amene amachiza matenda obwera chifukwa cha tizirombo ta bacteria (antimicrobial resistant strains), nthawi yomweyo kupitiliza kukweza thanzi la nyama.

Tikufuna tikafufuze kufala kwa matenda ena ambiri amene amafala kuchokera ku nyama kupita kwa anthu m'Malawi. Nthawi yomweyo kutenga zoyesa za chimbudzi, mulingo wochepera wa magazi zidzatengedwa ku ziweto (ng'ombe, nkhusa, mbuzi, nkhumba), ziweto monga (agalu ndi amphaka) komanso nyama monga makoswe (rodents). Ntchito yoyeza idzachitika pa magazi awa pofuna kupeza ngati nyama m'Malawi zili pa chiopyezo chotengera matendawa. Tidzafunanso kuunika zoyesa za chimbudzi zimene zingatengedwe kuchokera ku chimbudzi cha nyama pofuna kupeza ngati muli nyongolosi komanso timazira timene timanyamula tizirombo toyambitsa matenda (parasite eggs), zimene zitasonyeze mulingo wa chipsyinjochi cha tizirombo toyambitsa matendati umene umakhudza nyama.

NDICHIFUKWA CHANI NDIKUFUNSIDWA KUTENGA NAWO MBALI?

Mukufunsidwa kutenga nawo mbali chifukwa choti nyumba yanu ili mkati-kati mwa dela kumene kukuchitikira kafukufuku ku Chikwawa. Nyumba yanu yasankhidwa mwachisawawa pa nyumba zimene zili mdelamo, pogwiritsa ntchito software ya makina a kompyuta.

CHITACHITIKE NDI CHANI KWA ANTHU KOMANSO NYAMA ZIMENE ZIKUKHUDZIDWA?

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N'kutheka kuti maulendo atatu-anayi adzachitika pakhomopo musabata yopitilira imodzi. Ma ulendo otsatila apakhomo adzakonzedwa pambuyo pa mwenzi umodzi, komanso miyezi isanu ndi umodzi kuchokela ulendo oyamba wa kafukufuku pofuna kubweleza kutenga zoyesa. Pachiyambi ntchitoyi idzakambidwa ndi mutu wa banja ndipo chilorezo chidzatengedwa kuti ntchito yotenga zoyesa za mamembala komanso nyama za m'nyumbamu. Chilorezo chidzatengedwa kuchokera kwa membala wa m'nyumbamo payekha-payekha kutsimikizira kuti ndiokondwa kutenga nawo mbali mu ntchitoyi. Anthu akulu-akulu (kaya kholo kapena wopereka chisamaliro), adzapereka chilorezo chomveka bwino kwa ana osaposeza zaka 18, ndipo ana azaka 8-18 adzapereka chilorezo chomveka bwino kuti ndiokondwa kutenga nawo mbali mu ntchitoyi.

CHITACHITIKE NDI CHANI PA ZOYESA ZANGA?

Zoyesa za chimbudzi zimene zatengedwa zidzatumizidwa ku malo oyezerako zinthu a **Liverpool-Malawi Wellcome Trust Laboratories**, Queen Elizabeth Hospital, Blantyre kumene ntchito yoyeza zinthu itadzachitikire. Bacteria amene amakuzidwa pa zoyesa, kapena DNA kuchokera ku ma bacteriawo, zidzatumizidwa ku UK kuti ntchito ya **whole genome sequencing** ikachitike. Zoyesa za magazi za nyama zikhoza kutumizidwa ku UK kuti zikagwiridwe ntchito, ngati pangapezeke kuti palibe Zoyesa zoyenelera ku Malawi. Palibe zoyesa za anthu zitadzatuluke m'Malawi.

KODI NDIDZAFUNSIDWA KUPEREKA UTHENGA WANJI?

Pofuna kuthandizira mamvetsedwe a zotsatira zopezeka mu ntchitoyi, ntchito yotenga zoyesa isanachitike, tidzakupemphani kupereka uthenga wotsatirawu, ngati zikudziwika, zokhudzana ndi nyumba yanu:

1. Uthenga wa mamembala a nyumbayi
2. Mwini wa nyama
3. Matenda amene anthu komanso nyama zadwalapo m'mbuyomu
4. Mankhala a antibiotic amene anagwiritsidwa ntchito mkati-kati mwa nyumbayi (anthu komanso nyama)
5. Za chilengedwe zimene zazungulira nyumbayi
6. Chisamaliro chochitika mkati-kati mwa nyumba

Zimenezi ndizofuna kutipatsa uthenga wofunikira pamene tikufufuza zotsatira za kafukufukuyu.

KODI KAFUKUFUKUYU ADZABWERETSA CHANI PA INE?

ZIOPSYEZO

Palibe mavuto amene atadzakumane nawo mamembala komanso nyama zokhala m'nyumbamu.

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PHINDU

Kafukufukuyu adzatithandizira kupeza nzeru pa njira zimene kachiroombo ka *E. coli* komanso non-typhoidal *Salmonella* kamafalira mkati-kati mwa nyumba.

Kafukufukuyu adzapeza ngati kusagwira ntchito kwa mankhwala ophera tizirombo toyambitsa matenda mthupi (antimicrobial) kukukhudza kuonongeka kwa kachiroombo ka *E. coli* komanso non-typhoidal *Salmonella kamene* kamanyamulidwa ndi mamembala a nyumbayi.

Kafukufukuyu adzapeza ngati nyama mkati-kati mwa nyumba zakhalapo pa chiopyezo chotengera tizirombo toyambitsa matenda kuchokera ku nyama kupita kwa munthu (zoonotic pathogens) kapena ngati ali pachipsyinjio pa nthawi oytenga zoyesa.

NDINDANI ATADZAGWIRITSE NTCHITO UTHENGA UMENE UTADZATOLEREDWE PA INE?

Uthenga umene ungatoleredwe pa nthawi imene kafukufuku akuchitika udzakhala wa chinsinsikomanso udzagwiritsidwa ntchito ndi Dr Catherine Wilson yekha. Zoyesa zonse zidzaikidwa malo amodzi komanso zopanda kukhala ndi dzina pamayambiro olowetsedwa mu **database ya** kafukufuku. Pakapezeka zotsatira zina zilizonse zofunikira, kudzera mu chilorezo chanu, uthengawu udzalembedwa m'mabuku oyenelera a sayansi pofuna kukuza nzeru zosiyana-siyana komanso kafalidwe ka kachiroombo ka *E. coli* komanso *Salmonella* pakhomo pofuna kupereka njira yoyenelera pofuna kuchepetsa kufala kwa matenda.

KODI NDIZADZIWA ZA ZOTSATIRA ZA KAFUKUFUKUYU?

Ntchito yofufuza deta mukafukufuku ikadzatha kuchitika, tidzapereka lipoti la zotsatira ku **Malawi Veterinary Authorities**. Pakadzapezeka mavuto pa zotsatira zimene zingadzakhudze nyumba yanu molunjika, tidzakudziwitsani za izi ndikukupatsani uphungu pa zoyenera zimene mukuyenera kutsatira zokhudzana ndi umoyo.

CHITACHITIKE NDI CHANI NDIKAPANDA KUFUNA KUTENGA NAWO MBALI?

Ngakhale kuti thandizo lanu pantchitoyi idzalemekezedwa kwambiri; palibe zotsatira zina zilizonse zimene zingakhalepo mukakana kutenga nawo mbali. Sitidzakuyenderaninso kunyumba kwanu pa nkhani yokhudzana ndi ntchitoyi. Zikomo kwambiri chifukwa chowerenga chikalata cha uthengachi.

NDINGAPITE KWA NDANI KUTI NDI MVE ZAMBIRI ZOKHUDZANA NDI IZI?

Adilesi ya kumalo kumene mumakhala komanso uthenga wa m'mene mungalumikizirane ndi mkulu wa kafukufuku (PI):

Catherine Wilson

Adilesi: Malawi-Liverpool-Wellcome Trust Centre, Queen's Hospital, Blantyre, Malawi,

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Adilesi ya kumalo kumene mumakhala komanso uthenga wa m'mene mungalumikizirane ndi komiti yoyang'anira za ufulu wa anthu mukafukufuku:

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